

Which AI harms and risks will mobilise the public to act?

MARKUS OSTAREK, CATHY ROGERS,
BEN KENWARD & SAM NADEL

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Executive summary

What will it take to get people to act on AI harms and risks? Despite high levels of public concern and strong support for regulation, there has not yet been widespread public action. Currently, powerful tech industry interests are shaping outcomes largely unchallenged. This study, the first of its kind in the UK, investigates what might close the gap between concern and mobilisation.

We conducted a randomised controlled trial with 3,467 UK participants, each randomly assigned to read a vignette (a short, news-like text of roughly 100 words) about one of eleven AI harms/risks - or a control with no vignette. We measured the effect of reading that vignette on their concern and willingness to act.

Key findings:

- **The risk of AI-enabled warfare - autonomous weapons like robots and drones which operate without meaningful human oversight - caused the greatest level of concern about AI in general.** When people read about AI-enabled warfare, they agreed more that AI is a threat, that we should slow down its development, and that we should regulate it. It was the only risk which shifted people on all these measures. It was also the only risk that affected people's voting preferences.
- **Environmental harm most galvanised people to act;** people were substantially more willing to act on environmental harms of AI after reading about them, suggesting this issue has high mobilisation potential. The other issue that saw a similar boost was the harm caused by **AI bias and discrimination** suggesting it too could be a productive issue to campaign on.
- **The extinction risk posed to humanity by AI (X-risk) had the lowest level of concern of any harm/risk.** Reading about X-risk made little difference to how concerned people felt about it. One way to boost X-risk concern is indirect: **reading about AI-enabled warfare increased concern about X-risk substantially more than reading about X-risk itself.** Concrete, present-day harms may be a better way to communicate on X-risk.
- **The psychological drivers** of willingness to take action were **anger** (not anxiety or fear), **perceived temporal proximity of the risk (sooner being stronger)** and **concern for others** rather than oneself.

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- **Job displacement - by far the most salient concern in surveys - ranked surprisingly low** on mobilisation potential, suggesting an issue's salience is not a reliable proxy for its mobilisation potential.
- **Any messaging about AI harms increases people's general sense of concern about AI.** This is important for campaigners of all kinds and suggests a deficit of existing public knowledge of AI harms/risks.
- **Over a quarter of all participants clicked through to sign an AI regulation petition,** an unusually high proportion, a signal of significant latent concern.
- Overall, the public is worried about AI. What they lack is a feeling of anger and a sense that channeling it will make a difference. The movements already gaining traction - communities blocking data centres, coalitions campaigning against autonomous weapons - are succeeding because they connect AI's abstract harms to things people can see, feel and fight. This study suggests that many of the ingredients for a broader AI movement are already in place: there is high concern, it is spread across several disparate AI harms and risks, and people's willingness to take action, at least on some of those risks, appears to be malleable.

Keywords: AI risks, AI harms, public mobilisation, AI regulation, AI safety, existential risk, extinction risk, X-risk, autonomous weapons, environmental harms, AI-enabled warfare, job displacement

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is changing the world before our eyes. [Most people](#) feel an ambivalence about its development, seeing both the potential good AI might bring as well as its current or potential harms. Uppermost in people's roster of concerns, [according to multiple surveys](#), are the risks of job displacement, misinformation, disinformation and increasing levels of surveillance its development is heralding. A consistent finding across surveys is that a majority - between 60 and 80% of people - support AI regulation, with even larger numbers wanting to regulate certain high danger applications such as autonomous weapons.

Despite widespread concerns and broad support for AI regulation, AI remains a low salience issue; when people are asked about the issues that matter most to them, AI ranks low. This creates a potentially dangerous policy vacuum; when issues lack public salience, elite and institutional players tend to determine outcomes. In the current environment, this means the extraordinarily powerful tech lobby, who have [a low level of public trust](#) and a [US administration disposed towards acceleration](#). Just one illustration of this is the AI industry super PAC *Leading the Future*, backed by leading tech company players, which actively opposes candidates who support AI regulation and which, according to [one estimate](#), raised \$125 million in 2025. These decisions about how AI develops will affect every one of us. But those decisions are currently happening outside meaningful public engagement.

It needn't be this way. History shows that mobilising the public on an issue - raising its salience - can alter policy outcomes even against powerful opposition. Evidence from movements fighting for civil rights, climate action, abortion, marriage equality, and many more issues, shows that people-powered movements can change the political maths.

The challenge - and the rationale for this study - is that we don't yet know enough about what will mobilise people on AI. So far, high levels of concern haven't translated into meaningful action. There is a "mobilisation gap" - the gap between caring and doing. This research investigates what might close that gap.

The public cares

We know from [multiple surveys in many countries](#) that [the public](#) is strongly in favour of regulation of AI. Across the UK, US and globally the percentage of people expressing a desire for AI regulation is between 55 and 82%, while the percentage opposing it is in the

10-20% range. The remainder are on the fence. Support for regulation is also [growing](#), as AI continues to develop and expand into more aspects of our lives. In the UK support went from 66% in 2020 to 80% in 2022; in the US from 57% to 66% in the same period. There are some differences between demographic groups - for instance, women generally show higher levels of concern than men, and older people are more worried than younger people. At a global level, China and India are generally much more positive and optimistic about the future of AI than the US, UK and Europe.

But people are not very vocal in their concerns

There are several organisations focused on countering different AI harms and risks and encouraging greater public involvement in AI developments (we outline several in our [AI mapping report](#)). However, despite people's high levels of concern about AI and strong demand for regulation, there has not been widespread public action on AI. There is a gap between concern and demonstrable expression of that concern; this is not unusual as there are many areas of government policy where people have strong feelings when asked, despite there being little public demonstration of those feelings. With AI, there are two exceptions; one is the recent growth of protests against the build out of data centres in the US, which by an estimate from the organisation [Data Centre Watch](#), [blocked or delayed nearly \\$100billion of data centre projects](#) in just 3 months in 2025. The other comprises those groups seeking to mobilise the public against the threat to humanity of extinction ('X-risk') posed by AI - groups such as [Control AI](#), [Pause AI](#), [Stop AI](#), and the [Future of Life Institute](#). They have had some success in galvanising large numbers of the public to sign petitions; at the time of writing, 135,384 people, including many high profile figures, have signed the [Statement on superintelligence](#) calling for a prohibition on the development of superintelligence.¹

An important goal of this study is to understand what concerns people most concretely, and what is most likely to persuade them to act on those concerns.

¹ The "Statement on AI risks" signed by leading AI scientists and CEOs in May 2023 also said that "Mitigating the risk of extinction from AI should be a global priority alongside other societal-scale risks such as pandemics and nuclear war" ([Center for AI Safety, 2023](#))

What do we know so far about people's attitudes to AI risks?

Two studies have explored what might motivate the public to act on AI. Both found that people respond more strongly to immediate, tangible harms - particularly job loss and risks to children - than to more abstract scenarios. [Hoes and Gilardi's pre-registered experiments](#) with over 10,800 US and UK participants also found that exposure to existential risk narratives increased concern about catastrophic scenarios without reducing concern for immediate harms, suggesting people can hold multiple AI worries simultaneously. The [2025 Trippenbach et al study](#) from Seismic Foundation also examined mobilisation potential, using a method of maximum difference scaling with 1,063 US respondents. They presented people with sets of four AI risk statements (each about a different risk) and asked which would most mobilise them to act. Their findings confirmed that job disruption and threats to children resonate most strongly across demographic groups and that people tend not to engage with catastrophic risk narratives.

In our own study we had a single open-ended question which is relevant here. We asked all participants, "Could you tell us in 1 or 2 sentences how you feel about the development of AI?" This question gives a good sense of issue salience, since unlike the rest of the survey (which asks for reactions to presented information), it captures the issues spontaneously uppermost in people's minds. Our findings were in line with discussed studies: the top harm/risk area, by some margin, was threats to jobs and the workplace. Existential / extinction risk was mentioned by very few people, and even when it was, several wrote of their skepticism of this risk being a real one. More details of these qualitative findings are outlined in [this blog](#); we will publish full details soon in an additional short report.

Methods (in brief)

The full methodology is detailed [at the end of the report](#). Briefly, we conducted a [pre-registered](#) randomised controlled trial where online participants were randomly assigned to one of eleven treatment conditions or a control. The treatment conditions were all vignettes (short, news-like articles of roughly 110 words) detailing one of eleven specific AI harm/risk issues. An example vignette for each harm/risk is at the end of this report. Participants read such a vignette, then answered questions, while those in a control condition answered the same questions without reading a vignette. The harm/risk areas were:

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- **Job displacement** where AI systems could reshape half of all jobs in developed economies
- **Misinformation** where AI-generated content makes it hard to distinguish truth from fiction
- **Disinformation** where AI tools enable deceit, targeted abuse and hateful content at scale
- **Human extinction risk**, where advanced AI systems could pose catastrophic threats to humanity
- **Surveillance**, where AI systems enable citizens to be monitored without their knowledge or consent
- **Autonomous weapons**, where AI-controlled systems make life-or-death decisions without human approval
- **Social isolation**, where AI companions could replace human relationships
- **Bias** due to AI systems discriminating based on race and gender, affecting critical decisions, such as who gets job interviews or welfare benefits
- **Environmental harm**, where AI data centres strain water and energy resources
- **AI-enabled fraud**, where voice cloning and deep fakes are used to scam vulnerable people
- **Loss of human capabilities and cognitive decline**, where reliance on AI means people lose the ability to think and do things for themselves

The total number of participants was 3,467 with approximately 290 participants randomly assigned to each condition. Respondents were recruited online via [Prolific](#), selected so as to be nationally representative for age, gender, and political affiliation, and answered the survey online, via [Qualtrics](#). The full survey questions are included in the [supplementary materials](#).

Results - main findings

In this report, we highlight those findings that we believe to be of greatest interest to campaigners and strategists looking to galvanise people on AI risks and harms. Note that all our findings are described in full, in the order of the analyses we carried out, in [section 1 of the supplementary materials](#). There, you will find additional information about responses to each risk area. Here, for the sake of clarity, we focus on four key findings.

1. Reading about AI-enabled warfare increases general AI concern, X-risk concern, and shifts voting preferences

What is this risk?

The risk of [AI-enabled warfare](#) refers to the concern that autonomous weapons, AI-controlled drones, and other AI-based warfare systems may increasingly be used without human oversight. Such systems may lack the judgement that humans have to make life-and-death decisions. In a [recent dispute](#) between the US Department of War and Anthropic, Dario Amodei (CEO of Anthropic) argued that Claude should not be used for autonomous weapons because it is not reliable enough for such purposes.

Who is working on it?

[Future of Life Institute](#) has long worked on both [autonomous weapons](#) and broader human extinction risk. It has produced influential films such as the [Slaughterbots](#) series, maintains an [autonomous weapons database](#) tracking systems under development globally, and advocates for a new international treaty prohibiting weapons that target humans without meaningful human control. Their open letters have attracted over 34,000 signatories. Other campaign groups have been actively working to draw attention to the harms of autonomous weapons. [Stop Killer Robots](#) has been working on this issue for decades, building momentum for legally binding international regulations, no small feat in the current geopolitical climate. Over 120 countries support treaty negotiations and the UN adopted a new General Assembly resolution in 2024.

What did people read about this risk?

As with all the harms and risks we examined, participants read a short vignette describing the harm in question. Details of the vignette design and examples of all the other vignettes can be found [here](#). Below is an example of the vignette on AI-enabled warfare.

Illustrative² vignette about AI-enabled warfare

Captain Rob, a 45-year-old Army officer from Portsmouth, recently participated in military exercises using AI-controlled drones that select targets without human approval. The systems operate at speeds quicker than human reaction time, making life-or-death decisions autonomously. Activists warn that autonomous weapons will spark uncontrollable conflicts that could spiral into global catastrophe in the coming decade. AI can process battlefield information faster than humans and operate in dangerous environments. However, these systems lack human judgment about which actions are proportionate and necessary in combat. Multiple nations are racing to develop autonomous weapons and other AI-enabled tools for warfare. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

What did we find?

Information about AI-enabled warfare most consistently increases general concern about AI.

In figure 1 below, we looked at a composite measure of general AI concern. The measure is made up of people's answers to three questions: agreement that AI is a threat, agreement that we should slow down AI development, and support for regulation of AI. All risk areas are associated with increased concern relative to the control condition. While most risk areas did not differ greatly, reading about AI-enabled warfare significantly increased general AI concern more than all other risk areas, except fraud and scams due to AI.

² Each vignette was varied across three dimensions - protagonist characteristics, messenger type, and reversibility framing - yielding 88 unique stimuli across the 11 treatment conditions. More detail on this is given in the full methods section below.

Which AI harms and risks will mobilise the public to act?

Figure 1. The degree to which reading about different harms/risks increases general concern about AI, relative to the control group (red dotted line).

In figure 2, we show the analysis for those same three components individually. Here we see some interesting differences. Generally, there is a consistent pattern across risk areas; relative to the control condition, reading about AI risks strongly increased people's agreement that AI is a threat, but barely moved support for government regulation of AI. Agreement that we should slow down AI development sits in-between the two. AI-enabled warfare is the only condition that credibly shifted people on all three measures; it increased agreement that AI is a threat, *and* that we need to slow down AI development, *and* increased support for greater government regulation of AI.

Treatment Effects on AI Concern Measures vs Control

Posterior distributions across the three measures

Figure 2. The degree to which reading about different harms/risks increases the view that AI is a threat (pink), that AI development should be slowed (yellow) and that AI should be regulated (green), relative to the control group (black dotted line).

Information about AI-enabled warfare affects voting preferences

We asked participants, after reading the vignette, how it would affect their likelihood of voting for a party that made dealing with AI risks a priority. The possible answers ranged from “Would make it much less likely that I’d vote for them” to “Would make it much more likely that I’d vote for them”. AI-enabled warfare was the only condition that - relative to the control - credibly increased participants’ likelihood of saying they would be more inclined to

vote for such a party. The results are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Effect of reading about different AI risk areas on the extent to which people's intention to vote for a party would be affected by that party making AI risks a priority, relative to control (red dotted line). Blue shadings signify statistically robust effects (for which the 95%CI does not include zero).

2. When people read about the environmental harms of AI, they become much more willing to act.

What is this risk?

The environmental harms of AI stem primarily from the enormous physical infrastructure needed to power the technology. While the carbon footprint of any individual using an AI chatbot is [negligible](#), the aggregate picture is very different. Training and running large AI models demands [vast amounts of electricity](#), much of which is still generated from fossil fuels, and which can increase local energy costs for public consumers. Data centres also

consume [huge quantities of water](#) for cooling, placing strain on local water supplies, particularly in drought-prone regions. Beyond energy and water, the rapid expansion of AI infrastructure carries risks such as [habitat destruction](#), intensive extraction of rare earth minerals and other raw materials, growing volumes of electronic waste and [various forms of pollution](#) associated with manufacturing and disposal. As AI adoption accelerates, these environmental costs are expected to grow substantially.

Who is working on it?

In the US, as a result of these harms, a substantial movement has grown to protest the build out of data centres. [Data Centre Watch](#), an organisation that tracks this growing movement, estimates that hundreds of billions of dollars of data centre projects have been blocked or delayed as a result of these protests. In the UK, the data centre movement is beginning to coalesce, with a mix of national and local groups. [Action to Protect Rural Scotland](#) is [calling for a moratorium](#) on data centre construction in Scotland, and has [created a map](#) of planned projects to encourage others to join them. [Global Action Plan UK](#) called on people to join the recent [March against the Machines](#) as part of their campaign to challenge Big Tech and backing many local groups challenging the unchecked expansion of data centres.

What did people read about it in our study?

As with all harms and risks in our study, participants read a short vignette describing one of these in a short vignette. Design details can be found [here](#) and below is an example of the vignette on environmental harm.

Illustrative vignette about environmental harms

Dan, a 39-year-old farmer from rural Lincolnshire, noticed his water supply running low during a recent drought. He discovered a nearby AI data centre was consuming millions of gallons of water daily for cooling. Environmental scientists warn that the rapid expansion of AI and data centres will create an unsustainable burden on natural resources, straining electricity grids and depleting water supplies in the coming decade. Each query to advanced AI systems uses energy and water resources. Training large language models also produces significant carbon emissions. AI companies are rapidly building massive data centres, often in areas already facing water or energy scarcity. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

What did we find?

Our main finding was that reading about environmental harms substantially increased people's willingness to act on this harm. This can be seen in figure 4, in the difference between the grey and the purple distributions for this risk, which show willingness to act having read about that risk (purple) and willingness to act on that risk having read about a different risk (grey). While for many harms/risks, reading about them did not make much difference (i.e., the grey and the purple distributions are very similar), for environmental harms there was a significant difference - representing the fact that reading about this risk substantially increased people's willingness to act, such that this became the risk which people were most willing to act on.

The other harm/risk area that saw a similar boost in willingness to act as a result of reading about it was **bias and discrimination due to AI**. This arises when the outputs from automated systems systematically disadvantage particular groups - whether by race, gender, age, disability, or other characteristics. This can happen both through AI models being trained on historical data that reflects existing societal inequalities, and through datasets used for training being unrepresentative of the populations they are meant to serve. The consequences are most acute in high-stakes decisions such as hiring, credit-scoring, healthcare, and criminal justice, where AI-driven discrimination can be applied instantaneously across millions of decisions - making it both harder to detect and harder to challenge than individual human bias. In the US, the [Algorithmic Justice League](#) campaigns for accountability in AI systems and supports affected communities, while the [AI Now Institute](#) has produced influential research documenting discriminatory impacts across public sector uses of AI. In the UK, the [Ada Lovelace Institute](#) has examined how algorithmic decision-making affects marginalised groups, and [Foxglove Legal](#) has brought legal challenges against government use of discriminatory automated systems.

Willingness to act for each risk area

For people who read about that risk vs another risk

Figure 4. Willingness to act (a composite score of four items on a 1-5 scale) on different AI harms/risks for those who had read a vignette about that risk (purple) versus those who read a vignette about another risk (grey).

3. People were least concerned about the risk of human extinction (X-risk), but there are other effective ways to communicate about X-risk.

What is this risk?

Human extinction risk due to AI concerns the possibility that the development of superintelligent systems - AI that surpasses human abilities across all domains - could pose an irreversible threat to humanity's survival. The concern arises because as advanced AI systems grow more capable they are becoming harder to understand and control. A system that can improve itself recursively could rapidly exceed human intelligence in ways that are neither predictable nor reversible. If it pursued goals misaligned with human survival the results could be catastrophic. A significant number of leading AI researchers take this seriously: the [2023 joint statement](#) signed by AI CEOs, Nobel laureates, and hundreds of researchers declared that mitigating the risk of extinction from AI should be a global priority alongside pandemics and nuclear war.

Who is working on it?

In the UK, several organisations are working to translate this concern into action. [Control AI](#) has taken a policy-focused approach, briefing parliamentarians and building a cross-party coalition of UK lawmakers calling for binding regulation and a prohibition on the development of superintelligence; they also encourage the UK public to write to their MPs on the issue. [Pause AI](#) has adopted a more grassroots mobilisation approach, staging protests outside AI labs in King's Cross and calling for a global pause on frontier AI development. [Pull the Plug](#) is not focused exclusively on X-risk but on a range of AI harms and risks; their focus is on meaningful public participation in AI regulation and decision-making and they are calling for binding citizens' assemblies on AI. [Stop AI](#) are campaigning for a permanent ban on the development of artificial general intelligence and have engaged in various acts of nonviolent civil disobedience. These groups are beginning to coordinate: in February 2026, Pause AI and Pull the Plug jointly organised the 'March Against The Machines' in London.

What did people read about it in our study?

As with all the harms/risks, people read a short vignette detailing an example of this risk and how it might affect people.

Illustrative vignette about extinction risk

Dr. Sara, a 28-year-old technology ethics expert, recently testified before a parliamentary select committee to express concerns about the current path of AI development. As AI systems become superintelligent, there's a growing risk they could, deliberately or accidentally, bring about human extinction. Activists are now imploring society to stop developing superintelligent AI without adequate safeguards. As they grow more capable, AI systems are becoming harder to understand and control. Advanced AI could also start to improve itself, quickly becoming much more intelligent than humans and increasingly beyond human reach. Superintelligent AI systems might pursue goals which conflict with human wellbeing and even human survival. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

What did we find?

There are a few important findings regarding X-risk. First, of all the AI harms/risks we asked about, people are least concerned about X-risk (figure 5, chart on left). Second, people are also less willing to act on this risk than on nearly every other risk (only social isolation came lower). Third, reading about X-risk does not make much difference to people's concern or willingness to act on it - this is shown in the fact there is little difference between the grey and purple shaded areas in the chart on the right of figure 5 (note that this is the same chart as figure 4 above).

Concern and willingness to act for each risk area

For people who read about that risk vs another risk

Figure 5. Concern (left) and willingness to act (right) on different harms/risks, on a 1-5 scale, showing those who have read about that risk (purple) and those who have not read about that risk (grey).

While this is not hugely encouraging for X-risk campaigners, there was an encouraging finding, shown in figure 6: reading about AI-enabled warfare and environmental harms due to AI significantly increased people’s concern about X-risk relative to the control condition. Reading about AI-enabled warfare also increased X-risk concern more than reading about X-risk itself. *In other words, people are more concerned about X-risk if they read about AI-enabled warfare than if they actually read about X-risk.* We see a similar pattern for willingness to act on X-risk, where again reading about AI-enabled warfare increased people’s concern for X-risk³. An implication of these findings, put simply, is that X-risk campaigners would likely benefit from talking more about AI warfare.

³ Note that here this was the case relative to the control condition but not relative to reading about X-risk itself.

Spillover effects on attitudes towards X-risk

X-risk concern and willingness to act for each condition

Figure 6. Effect of reading about different AI harms/risks on X-risk concern (left) and willingness to act on X-risk (right), relative to the control group (red dotted line). Blue shading indicates that the effect is statistically robust (the 95%CI did not cross zero).

4. What underlies people's willingness to act?

We were interested in the factors that explain the impact of reading about a risk on a person's willingness to act on that risk. What turns a latent concern into a willingness to do something about it? To assess this, we focused on what specifically predicts the increase in a participant's willingness to act on the risk they read about. The analysis factored out people's inclination to act on other AI risks to get specifically at what determines increased willingness to take action on a given risk as a result of exposure to information about it.

We tested a number of potential factors, including emotions that may be triggered by the texts. Figure 7 shows the factors that explained a significant share of the willingness to act boost from reading about a given risk. In summary, willingness to take action on the risk a person read about was boosted more:

- If they expected the risk to become a real threat **sooner rather than later**

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- As a function of how much **other people they care about** might be affected. Surprisingly, perceived *personal* risk did not affect people's willingness to act.
- As a function of **how angry they felt** after having read about the risk. Anger was the only emotion that credibly explained the willingness boost (not other emotions such as anxiety, fear, powerlessness, sympathy for those affected).
- The **more positive their prior attitudes to AI were**. This could be because people with more positive attitudes towards AI might have been less exposed previously to information about AI risks, or considered AI risks less, or found such worries more overblown until reading the vignette (compared to people with more negative prior attitudes toward AI)

Figure 7. Psychological factors which account for the impact of reading about an AI risk on people's willingness to act on that risk. The analysis predicts the difference between a participant's willingness to act on the risk they read about minus their willingness to act on risks they did not read about. Effect sizes are indicated by the position of the posterior probability densities (larger effects are further to the right)

and the model's level of certainty about the effect size estimates is reflected in how spread out the posterior probabilities are (taller and thinner distributions reflect higher certainty).

Discussion and recommendations for the AI movement

Tapping into people's concern about AI warfare could be effective, especially now.

Any kind of messaging about AI harms and risks increases people's concern about AI to a meaningful extent. All eleven treatment conditions produced higher levels of general AI concern than the control group, and the differences between specific risk areas were generally small, with substantial overlap in their distributions. When zooming in on the three measures making up our general AI concern composite measure, AI-enabled warfare stood out as the only risk area that credibly increased people's agreement that AI is a threat, their agreement that we should slow down AI development, and support for AI regulation. AI-enabled warfare was also the only risk area for which our data indicated that it might affect how people vote; after reading about AI-enabled warfare, people indicated that a party standing on a platform to address AI risks would significantly increase the chance that they'd vote for them in the next election.

These findings, in combination with previous polling showing 61% people across 26 countries [oppose lethal autonomous weapons](#), are of particular potency in the current context of global conflict. As we write, the US and Israel have launched [major military strikes on Iran](#), with Iran retaliating across the region. Anthropic's AI tool Claude has been [reportedly used to identify and prioritise targets](#). In Ukraine, AI-guided autonomous strike drones are now [deployed at industrial scale](#), with drones responsible for over 80% of all enemy targets destroyed. Israel's use of AI targeting systems in Gaza - which can [generate bombing targets far faster than human analysts](#) - has drawn widespread concern about the erosion of human control over life-and-death decisions. The recent [dispute](#) between Anthropic and the Pentagon signals that the US government is keen to ramp up its use of AI in warfare, even when they are being warned that current AI systems are not reliable enough for such purposes.

For movement organisers, this might present a sombre window of opportunity: messaging that connects AI development to ongoing military conflicts may tap into existing public attention in ways that more abstract risk framings cannot. Prior research indicates that highlighting the error-prone nature of AI systems may be [particularly effective](#) for mobilising the public in support of regulation.

AI-enabled warfare also displayed intriguing spillover effects, affecting people's attitudes towards X-risk (see below). An interesting question for future research that our design did not address is whether information about AI-enabled warfare also affects how people think about additional/other risks. If it increases concern/willingness to act on additional AI risks, this would make it an even stronger issue for campaigners to focus on.

Environmental harms as a mobilisation opportunity

Environmental harms from AI emerged as one of the most promising areas for mobilisation. The risk of environmental harms topped the rankings for willingness to act on a risk after reading about it. Perhaps more importantly, environmental harms showed one of the strongest malleability effects: people's concern and willingness to act shifted significantly after reading about the issue, suggesting this is a risk area where public engagement campaigns could have real traction.

This aligns with what is already happening on the ground. In the United States, opposition to AI data centres has become one of the fastest-growing grassroots movements in the country. [Data Center Watch](#), a research organisation tracking this opposition, estimates that approximately \$98 billion in data centre projects were blocked or delayed in a single quarter of 2025, with 142 advocacy organisations now active across 28 states. The movement is unusual in cutting across political lines - as one organiser put it, opposition to data centres has united groups from left, right, and in-between around shared concerns about water depletion, rising electricity bills, and environmental degradation. [Food & Water Watch](#) led a coalition of over 230 environmental and community organisations in a letter to the US Congress demanding a national moratorium on new data centre construction. The [NAACP launched its "Stop Dirty Data Centers"](#) campaign, highlighting how AI infrastructure disproportionately burdens communities of colour, while [MediaJustice](#) published [The People Say No](#), documenting how tech companies are creating 'sacrifice zones' through data centre development across the American South.

Internationally, the [UN Environment Programme](#) has flagged AI's environmental footprint as a key topic for the UN Environment Assembly, and the [International Energy Agency](#) projects that electricity demand from data centres will [more than double by 2030](#). For UK-based campaigns, these American precedents offer a potential model, and the environmental framing has the advantage of connecting AI concerns to the existing climate movement infrastructure and activist base.

AI bias and discrimination as an additional mobilisation opportunity

Like environmental harms, AI bias and discrimination showed a meaningful boost in willingness to act after reading about it (and an even larger boost in concern) - suggesting it too has mobilisation potential. This is notable because it is a risk that affects many different communities and campaign groups. Bias and discrimination is already happening at scale and affects people in concrete, everyday ways - through mortgage rejections, job interview screening, benefit assessments, and interactions with the criminal justice system. This immediacy, combined with the anger it is likely to provoke, may help explain its mobilisation potential: our findings show that anger, more than other emotions, drives willingness to act. The experience of unjust treatment - whether personal or witnessed - is a reliable trigger for the moral outrage that spurs people to speak up.

In the UK, many groups are already tackling this issue on the ground. [Amnesty International UK](#) published a major report '[Automated Racism](#)' in 2025 documenting how predictive policing tools are amplifying racial discrimination through biased feedback loops; it is running a campaign to ban them. [StopWatch](#) and [Big Brother Watch](#) have been actively challenging discriminatory uses of facial recognition and algorithmic policing, while [Foxglove Legal](#) (who are also challenging the construction of data centres) have brought legal challenges against government use of discriminatory automated systems. The existing racial justice and civil rights movement infrastructure gives this issue an organisational base that other AI harm areas currently lack - a significant asset for campaigners looking to convert concern into action.

Implications for those working on human extinction risk

The findings present a challenging picture for organisations currently focused on communicating about extinction risks to the public. Concern about X-risk and willingness to act on X-risk were both very low, in absolute terms and relative to other risks we tested.

X-risk messaging does not appear to help much: even having read directly about X-risk, concern for X-risk was lower than concern for any other risk, and it had among the lowest willingness to act scores.

There is, however, a potential indirect route for communication. Reading about AI-enabled warfare and environmental harms due to AI substantially increased people's concern about X-risk through a spillover effect - much more than reading about X-risk itself⁴. This makes intuitive sense: autonomous weapons and environmental harms make the abstract concept of extinction threats from machines acting beyond human control tangible and immediate. For groups like the [Future of Life Institute](#), which works on both [autonomous weapons](#) (e.g., with their [Slaughterbots](#) film series and [autonomous weapons database](#)) and broader extinction risk, this finding strongly reinforces their dual-track strategy. This and the other findings showcasing the effectiveness of information on AI-enabled warfare are also encouraging for other campaign groups that have been drawing attention to the harms of autonomous weapons. [Stop Killer Robots](#), a coalition of over 250 organisations in 70 countries, co-founded by [Human Rights Watch](#), has built global momentum for a legally binding instrument - a treaty that would prohibit autonomous weapons that target people without meaningful human control and regulate others to ensure human oversight. Over 120 countries now support treaty negotiations and a landmark UN General Assembly resolution was adopted in December 2024, with only three states voting against.

The mobilisation gap

An important finding of this study is that concern does not straightforwardly translate into more active support for change. It is relatively easy to increase people's sense that AI is a threat to society, but harder to shift their agreement that AI development should be slowed, and harder still to increase support for government regulation. The only exception is AI-enabled warfare, which was the sole condition to credibly shift people on all three measures.

Another important finding challenges the assumption that issues with the highest salience are also those which are the most effective mobilisers. We know from [multiple surveys](#) as well as from our open-text question here, that the AI risk area most salient to people is job loss. Yet this is not the issue that, according to our data, stands out in terms of the levels of concern or willingness to act connected to it. Moreover, reading about job loss risks did not

⁴ However, it should be noted that even incorporating the boost from reading about AI-enabled warfare, X-risk concern was still lower than concern for nearly all other risk areas.

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increase concern or willingness to act on AI particularly strongly. For activists, this suggests that talking about job loss might be helpful in “meeting people where they are at” but that it might be more effective to move the conversation onto other topics, such as autonomous weapons and environmental harms, in order to see tangible actions.

The psychological factors that predict willingness to act reveal an important pattern: anger was the only emotional response that significantly predicted action, while anxiety, sympathy and feeling energised did not. Temporal proximity mattered; the sooner people perceived a harm as likely to become real, the more motivated they were to take action, a finding well-supported by [existing literature](#). A kind of altruism effect was also at play; people were more affected by the impacts they expected a risk to have on those they care about, than on themselves. This might be because, as seen in [other surveys](#), people are particularly concerned about the effects of AI on younger generations.

Surprisingly, people with more positive prior attitudes to AI showed greater willingness to act. Two possible explanations stand out. First, those who hadn't previously considered AI risks might have been more strongly affected by new information about them. Second, some might have previously considered risks but underestimated them - until reading a text that made a strong case for taking them seriously.

Our finding that job displacement ranks low on mobilisation potential diverges from [Trippenbach et al.'s study](#) from 2025, which found job disruption and threats to children to be the strongest mobilisers. Several explanations are possible. First, the studies used quite different methods: Trippenbach et al. employed maximum difference scaling, which asks participants to compare risks directly against one another and estimate which would be most and least likely to make them take action, whereas in our RCT, participants were exposed to information about a single risk and we measured how this exposure affected their willingness to act. This methodological distinction (measuring which risks people think they would be affected by most vs. directly measuring how risks affect people) could explain the differences in the results. Second, their sample was drawn from the US (vs. our UK sample), and cross-national differences in how people relate to job insecurity and other risk areas may explain some of the divergence. That said, both studies converge on one important point: people tend not to engage strongly with catastrophic or extinction-level risk narratives. Taken together, the mixed findings underscore the need for studies using consistent methods across multiple countries before drawing general conclusions about which AI harms have the greatest mobilisation potential.

It is important to highlight a limitation of the current study. Our primary outcomes are self-reported willingness to act and related attitudinal measures rather than actual observed behaviour. This is a well-known issue in the social sciences - there is a difference between what people say they will do and what they actually do; a [meta-analysis](#) found that changes in intention translate into [smaller changes in behaviour](#). Our design mitigates this concern to some extent, because our inferences are based on *relative* differences between risk framings rather than *absolute* levels of willingness for any particular risk area. Because participants are randomly assigned to conditions, any systematic inflation in reported willingness (e.g., from social desirability) would most likely be constant across conditions. Moreover, in line with the [social psychology of collective action](#), willingness to act is best understood as a proxy for mobilisation *potential* rather than a direct reflection/prediction of behaviour.

Petitions, voting and boycotting AI

The measures that came closest to measuring people's actual behaviour offer some encouraging signals alongside more complex results. When given the option to click through to sign an [AI safety petition](#) - a small but real action with a genuine time cost - over a quarter of participants (27%) chose to do so. This is a notable level of engagement, particularly given that respondents on the survey platform (Prolific) are paid for survey completion so have an incentive to finish quickly. A surprising finding was that those in the control condition were the most likely to sign the petition and there was little difference between the risk areas on this.

On voting intentions, reading about AI warfare made people significantly more likely to say they would vote for a party that prioritised addressing AI harms - suggesting that, for certain issues, AI policy could increasingly become electorally meaningful. Similarly, reading about disinformation credibly increased people's stated willingness to boycott AI tools, indicating that certain risk framings can shift consumer behaviour intentions. Such an approach is exemplified by a new campaign group [QuitGPT](#) which has attracted attention by asking users to boycott ChatGPT on the basis that "ChatGPT is Trump's biggest donor, and ICE uses ChatGPT. It's time to Quit." They claim that 700,000 have taken action as part of the boycott.

The autonomous weapons issue also connects to broader tech accountability movements: [People vs Big Tech](#), a European coalition of over 113 organisations from 23 EU member states, has already demonstrated how public mobilisation can shape tech regulation,

having played a critical role in shaping the EU's Digital Services Act and pushing for stronger AI safeguards. Their model of connecting corporate accountability to tangible harms could serve as a template for warfare-focused campaigns.

Zooming out to the broader risk landscape, our results suggest that none of the risk areas we tested diminished concern about X-risk relative to the control condition. For X-risk campaigners whose primary goal is mobilisation, this is reassuring: it appears viable to lead with issues that generate stronger public engagement - such as autonomous weapons, disinformation or environmental harm - and progress towards X-risk messaging later, without apparent risk of undermining concern about X-risk in the process.

Some potential barriers to mobilisation

As our findings show, the salience of an issue is not necessarily the best proxy for mobilisation. Job displacement is by far the most salient AI concern, consistently topping survey rankings, yet it does not rank highly on willingness to act. This disconnect may reflect a fatalism about job losses, or a sense that the problem is too large and diffuse for individual action to feel meaningful.

The fact that fear and anxiety score more highly than anger is also a potential barrier to mobilisation. People express high levels of concern but the dominant emotional response is anxiety rather than the moral outrage typically seen as driving activism. Fear and anxiety can easily trigger a flight, fright or freeze response - not the emotional state which typically brings people onto the streets. Many respondents in the qualitative results expressed a sense of passivity, that "someone should sort this out", without a sense that the someone might be them.

And some potential catalysts

Anger was the only emotion that significantly predicted willingness to act. This suggests that campaigns generating moral outrage about specific, attributable harms may be more effective than those that simply raise alarm about risks in the abstract. And one of our clearest findings is that simply informing people about any AI harm or risk increases their general concern about AI. The public is not apathetic, it is underinformed. When people learn about what is happening, they care more. On specific issues - environmental harms, autonomous weapons, algorithmic discrimination - that concern is demonstrably convertible into a willingness to act.

Finally, the broader ecosystem of organisations working on AI harms - from the [Future of Life Institute](#) and [Stop Killer Robots](#) on autonomous weapons, to [Food & Water Watch](#) and [Data Center Watch](#) on environmental harms, to [People vs Big Tech](#), [The Algorithmic Justice League](#), and the [DAIR Institute](#) on corporate accountability and digital rights, and so many others - represents a growing, if still fragmented, movement. Our findings suggest that different risk areas activate different constituencies, signalling the benefits of collaboration. A more coordinated movement that connects these threads - linking the tangible environmental harms of data centres to the governance questions around autonomous weapons to the everyday concerns about misinformation - could be more powerful than any single-issue campaign.

So where next? The case for action

The global AI picture is not reassuring. A handful of extraordinarily powerful technology companies are racing to build systems whose consequences they do not fully understand nor can fully control. Safety and caution are sidelined, while the [zealous conviction](#) that artificial general intelligence is both inevitable and desirable prevails. Governments that should be providing oversight are instead competing to attract AI investment, with the US administration actively [dismantling regulatory guardrails](#) and pouring resources into military AI applications.

In the UK, the foundations of a movement are already visible and strengthening. New groups are forming every week. As data centre proposals emerge, [grassroots groups](#) are forming to confront them. [QuitGPT](#) is channeling consumer power into a boycott of ChatGPT. Artist collectives are fighting back against the appropriation of their work. In February 2026, a coalition of groups came together for the [March Against the Machines](#) in London. Internationally, communities are [blocking billions of dollars of data centre projects](#), and over 120 countries are [backing a treaty](#) on autonomous weapons.

This emerging movement confronts strategic challenges that are far from straightforward. The issues at the front of people's minds are not necessarily the ones that will move them to act. The emotional responses that dominate are not the ones that drive mobilisation. Getting the strategy right matters, because the decisions being made now - about autonomous weapons, about the environmental costs of AI infrastructure, about who controls superintelligent systems - will shape the world for generations.

We hope this research is useful to the inspiring campaigners, organisers and advocates already doing this work, and to those considering joining them. What movements have, when they work at scale, is the passion, moral conviction and commitment to make an issue impossible to ignore. There is a public out there that already cares about AI, and whose concern can be converted into action. The job of the movement is to reach them. This study, and our AI research programme more broadly, aims to contribute to that effort.

Methods (in more detail)

Participants

We recruited a UK-representative sample (with respect to age, gender, and political affiliation) of adults aged 18 and older through the Prolific platform. Our target sample size was 3,200-3,500 participants across 12 conditions (~267-292 per condition), determined to provide >95% power to detect small-to-medium effects ($d = 0.25$) for pairwise comparisons between each treatment condition and the control. Data collection began on 10 January 2026 and continued until reaching the target sample size. Participants were required to be UK residents and fluent in English. We excluded participants with technical errors leading to incorrect display of study materials or with incomplete responses on key outcome measures. All participants provided informed consent. The study was pre-registered before any outcome data were examined (see Data availability).

Design

We employed a between-subjects randomised vignette experiment with 12 conditions: 11 treatment conditions, each presenting a different AI risk area, and one no-information control condition. Participants were randomly assigned to conditions through Qualtrics' randomisation function with equal probability for each condition. We verified successful randomisation through chi-square goodness-of-fit tests comparing observed versus expected frequencies across conditions, visual inspection of temporal distribution across the data collection period, and covariate balance checks.

The full set of survey questions can be found [here](#).

Experimental conditions

The 11 AI risk areas were selected through a review of AI risk literature and expert consultation, and comprised: (1) job displacement, (2) misinformation, (3) disinformation, (4) human extinction, (5) surveillance, (6) AI-enabled warfare, (7) social isolation, (8) bias and discrimination, (9) environmental harms, (10) sophisticated scams and fraud, and (11) loss of human capabilities and cognitive decline.

The details of the vignette design follows below.

Measures

We measured outcomes at two levels: general AI attitudes assessed for all participants (control and treatment), and risk-specific outcomes assessed only for treatment conditions.

General AI attitudes and mobilisation. We measured general AI concern using four items on a 5-point agreement scale (e.g., "The development of AI will threaten society", "We should slow down the development of AI until we understand its consequences"; two items reverse-coded). We assessed support for AI regulation with a single 5-point item. We constructed a composite measure from the two concern items and the regulation item (mean of three items; internal consistency assessed via Cronbach's alpha, with a decision rule that $\alpha < 0.60$ would trigger separate analysis of individual items). We also measured boycott intention (5-point scale), impact on voting preferences (5-point scale), and petition click behaviour (binary), where participants were invited to click through to a real petition about AI risks (the Future of Life petition).

Risk-specific outcomes. Each treatment participant rated concern (single 5-point item) and willingness to act (four items on a 5-point scale covering sharing on social media, contacting their local MP, donating, and joining an organisation; averaged into a composite) for three risk areas presented in random order: (a) their assigned risk (the one they read about), and (b) two other risk areas they did not read about. Critically, extinction risk always appeared as one of the "other" risks for participants not assigned to that condition, enabling consistent measurement of extinction risk attitudes across all participants.

Mechanism variables. For treatment participants only, we measured five emotional responses to the assigned vignette (anxious/fearful, angry, energised, hopeless/powerless, sympathetic; each on a 0-10 slider), personal relevance (0-10 slider), perceived affect on

people the participant cares about (0-10 slider), and temporal expectation of when the risk would become serious (5-point ordinal from "It's already happening" to "More than 20 years from now").

Covariates. We measured prior AI attitude (5-point scale), prior AI risk awareness (4-point scale), and AI tool usage frequency (7-point scale). Demographic variables included political party affiliation, education level, region, chief earner occupation, age, and gender (the latter two obtained from Prolific prescreening data). Due to an error during data collection, civic engagement information could not be used and was dropped from all analyses.

Attention check. Treatment participants answered a comprehension check identifying their vignette's headline from among 5-6 distractors. Control participants were assigned a score of 1 (correct) for this variable, on the assumption that control participants who completed the survey were attentive (sensitivity analyses tested robustness to this coding decision).

Statistical analysis

All analyses used Bayesian regression models fitted with the brms package in R, which interfaces with Stan. Models were fitted using 4 chains of 10,000 iterations each (5,000 warmup), with $\text{adapt_delta} = 0.95$ and $\text{max_treedepth} = 12$. Convergence was assessed via $R_{\text{hat}} < 1.01$, effective sample size ratios > 0.1 , absence of divergent transitions, and visual inspection of trace plots. We used model families appropriate to each outcome type: cumulative ordinal regression for single Likert items, Gaussian linear regression for averaged composites and 0-10 slider scales, and Bernoulli logistic regression for petition click.

Priors. We specified weakly informative priors informed by meta-analyses of vignette experiment effect sizes and similar studies. For ordinal models, we used Student- $t(3, 0, 2.5)$ for thresholds and Student- $t(3, 0, 0.5)$ for fixed effects, the latter expecting approximately 95% of effects to fall between -1 and +1 on the latent scale. For Gaussian models with 1-5 scale composites, we used Normal(4, 2) for intercepts and Student- $t(3, 0, 0.75)$ for fixed effects. For 0-10 scales, intercept priors were Normal(5, 3) with Student- $t(3, 0, 1)$ for fixed effects. Binary models used Student- $t(3, 0, 2.5)$ for intercepts and Student- $t(3, 0, 0.5)$ for fixed effects. All models included Exponential(1) priors for residual standard deviations where applicable. We chose Student- $t(3)$ distributions over normal or Cauchy priors as a balance between robustness to outliers and stable estimation.

Analysis set 1: treatment effects versus control. To test whether AI risk vignettes increase concern and mobilisation relative to the control condition (H1-H3), we regressed each general outcome (AI concern composite, boycott intention, voting preference, petition click) on risk condition (treatment-coded with control as reference) and covariates. Because the control condition has no vignette variants, these models could not include random intercepts for the vignette variants in the way we had pre-registered. The main analyses presented here estimated fixed-effects models for all analyses involving the control condition without random effects. To assess whether this simplification affected results, we took two measures: 1) we fitted equivalent models on treatment-only data both with and without random intercepts for variant (and additionally tested random slopes for risk area), finding negligible differences in parameter estimates ([see supplementary materials](#)). 2) We used syntax that does allow us to estimate random intercepts as pre-registered, as detailed in the [supplementary materials](#), which similarly showed nearly identical estimates.

Analysis set 2: comparing risk areas (treatment conditions only). To test whether reading about a specific risk increases concern and action intentions for that risk relative to other risks (H4), we restructured data so each participant contributed one "assigned risk" observation and one "other risk" observation (selected to balance representation across risk areas). We fitted models with a binary predictor (assigned versus other) and random intercepts for participant and variant. A separate set of models focused specifically on extinction risk as the outcome, testing whether reading about each risk area affected concern and willingness to act regarding extinction risk (H5), with random intercepts for variant and extinction risk as the reference condition.

Analysis set 3: mechanisms (exploratory). Conditional on finding meaningful differences in Analysis Set 2, we examined whether emotional responses, personal relevance, perceived affect on close others, and temporal expectations predicted mobilisation outcomes and explained variation across risk conditions. We first tested whether risk conditions differentially activated each mechanism, then tested whether mechanisms predicted mobilisation controlling for risk condition, and finally estimated proportion mediated using the product-of-coefficients approach.

Inference and reporting. We consider effects to be statistically robust if the 95% credible interval does not include zero. We do not apply multiple comparison corrections, as the regularising priors already guard against overfitting and we report full posterior distributions for all contrasts.

Deviations from pre-registration. Two changes from the pre-registered plan should be noted. First, civic engagement data could not be used due to a data collection error and was excluded from all analyses. Second, models comparing treatment conditions to control were estimated without random effects for vignette variants, as the control condition lacks variants. [Supplementary analyses](#) demonstrate that inclusion of random effects in treatment-only models does not meaningfully alter the pattern of results (see [supplementary materials](#)).

Vignettes

For all eleven harm/risk areas, we created short vignettes which presented a short case study of that harm/risk's manifestation in the world. Each vignette was approximately 110 words long (range: 103-119) and written in a neutral, journalistic style. Vignettes followed a consistent structure: a specific but not sensational headline; a concrete scenario centred on a named individual; a messenger statement elaborating on future projections using consensus-implying language (e.g., "A growing body of research suggests..."); further detail on implications; and a closing statement on reversibility.

We systematically varied three elements across vignettes to improve generalisability. Each risk category included eight variants crossing: (a) case study protagonist characteristics (name, age, location, profession; four male and four female names common across age groups and ethnicities, ages 28-62, mid-sized UK cities, professions relevant to the risk area), (b) messenger type (activists versus domain-relevant experts, e.g., "leading economists" or "defence analysts"), and (c) reversibility framing (addressable: "Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms" versus difficult to reverse: "Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo"). This yielded 88 unique vignette variants across the 11 treatment conditions.

Illustrative vignette 1. Job displacement

Helen, a 28-year-old bank cashier from Bolton, was recently made redundant. The reason? New AI software can do her team's work many times faster for a fraction of the cost. Helen is far from unique. Leading economists suggest that AI systems will reshape half of all jobs in developed economies in the coming decade. New AI systems can now do tasks which people thought would always need human experts. They can wade through long legal documents, write computer code, create spreadsheets in minutes. In the past, automation has mostly affected manual work,

but these developments mean any desk job is susceptible. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

Illustrative vignette 2. Autonomous weapons

Captain Rob, a 45-year-old Army officer from Portsmouth, recently participated in military exercises using AI-controlled drones that select targets without human approval. The systems operate at speeds quicker than human reaction time, making life-or-death decisions autonomously. Activists warn that autonomous weapons will spark uncontrollable conflicts that could spiral into global catastrophe in the coming decade. AI can process battlefield information faster than humans and operate in dangerous environments. However, these systems lack human judgment about which actions are proportionate and necessary in combat. Multiple nations are racing to develop autonomous weapons and other AI-enabled tools for warfare. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

Illustrative vignette 3. Misinformation

Emma, a 39-year-old teacher from Durham, shared a video of the Prime Minister announcing a new policy. Hours later, she discovered it was completely fake - an AI-generated 'deepfake'. Media experts warn that AI-generated content will make it very hard to distinguish truth from fiction in the coming decade. New AI systems create realistic videos, images and audio of events that never happened. The technology needs no expertise - anyone can create convincing fakes within minutes using free online tools. This includes fake news articles, fabricated scientific studies, and artificial social media accounts spreading propaganda. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

Illustrative vignette 4. Disinformation

Dan, a 47-year-old journalist from Leeds, wrote an article critical of a local business. Within hours, he faced a coordinated attack: embarrassing AI-generated deepfake videos using his face, fabricated quotes, and thousands of hateful messages from AI-powered bots. Digital safety researchers warn that AI tools will enable industrial-scale harassment campaigns targeting women, minorities, and vulnerable groups in the coming decade. AI systems generate convincing fake images and videos to harass individuals, create bot armies to coordinate attacks, and craft personalised threats. These tools require no expertise and operate at unprecedented scale. The

technology is increasingly used to enable targeted abuse and to silence critics. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

Illustrative vignette 5. Extinction risk

Dr. Sara, a 28-year-old technology ethics expert, recently testified before a parliamentary select committee to express concerns about the current path of AI development. As AI systems become superintelligent, there's a growing risk they could, deliberately or accidentally, bring about human extinction. Activists are now imploring society to stop developing superintelligent AI without adequate safeguards. As they grow more capable, AI systems are becoming harder to understand and control. Advanced AI could also start to improve itself, quickly becoming much more intelligent than humans and increasingly beyond human reach. Superintelligent AI systems might pursue goals which conflict with human wellbeing and even human survival. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

Illustrative vignette 6. Surveillance

Paul, a 28-year-old social worker from Luton, walked into a convenience store unaware that cameras were scanning his face and tracking his every move. The AI system built a detailed profile of his shopping habits, emotional state, and personal relationships. Activists warn that AI surveillance will eliminate privacy, putting every British citizen under constant corporate and government watch in the coming decade. AI can now identify individuals with high accuracy and infer sensitive information, including political views, health and financial status. Law enforcement agencies and private companies are rapidly deploying these systems with minimal oversight and the technology operates in public spaces across the country. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

Illustrative vignette 7. Social isolation

Sophie, a 51-year-old teacher from Norwich, recently discovered her son spends hours daily talking to an AI chatbot. He considers the chatbot his closest friend, and prefers its company to real-world friendships and family time. Activists warn that AI companions will displace genuine human relationships, leaving an entire generation socially isolated in the coming decade, and an uncontrollable epidemic of loneliness. AI chatbots are increasingly good at providing emotional support and companionship without the complications of real relationships. They're always available, never judgmental, and programmed to be agreeable. Many people are substituting complex human relationships with artificial ones. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

Illustrative vignette 8. Bias and discrimination

Dan, a 33-year-old teacher from Glasgow, applied for a mortgage and was denied one by an AI system. He later learned the algorithm had been trained on historical data reflecting decades of discriminatory lending. Researchers warn that AI systems are already amplifying existing inequalities affecting millions of Brits and that this will only get worse in the coming decade. AI learns from past data that reflects historical discrimination against women, racial minorities, and other marginalised groups. AI systems now influence several sectors, including who gets job interviews, medical treatments, welfare benefits, and probation decisions. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

Illustrative vignette 9. Environmental harms

Dan, a 39-year-old farmer from rural Lincolnshire, noticed his water supply running low during a recent drought. He discovered a nearby AI data centre was consuming millions of gallons of water daily for cooling. Environmental scientists warn that the rapid expansion of AI and data centres will create an unsustainable burden on natural resources, straining electricity grids and depleting water supplies in the coming decade. Each query to advanced AI systems uses energy and water resources. Training large language models also produces significant carbon emissions. AI companies are rapidly building massive data centres, often in areas already facing water or energy scarcity. Experts say, once established, these harms could be difficult to undo.

Illustrative vignette 10. Fraud and scams

Emma, a 39-year-old marketing executive from Manchester, received a call from her manager requesting a £12,000 transfer for an urgent supplier payment. She complied without hesitation. Hours later, she learned her manager's voice had been cloned by fraudsters using AI. Consumer protection agencies warn that AI will enable unprecedented levels of fraud in the coming decade. AI can now clone voices from short audio samples found online and generate convincing impersonations. Fraudsters use AI to analyse social media profiles and craft personalised scams, using deepfakes of trusted figures like family members or bank employees. These are increasingly sophisticated and difficult to detect. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

Illustrative vignette 11. Loss of cognitive capabilities

Paul, a 56-year-old HR manager from High Wycombe, recently realised he couldn't write a basic work email without AI assistance. He struggles to solve simple problems, plan projects, or think

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creatively without immediately turning to AI tools. Activists warn that AI dependency will create a generation incapable of independent thought, leaving people intellectually helpless in the coming decade. As AI systems handle increasingly complex tasks, people are losing the ability to think critically, solve problems independently, and retain knowledge. In the workplace, people increasingly depend on AI, outsourcing even basic reasoning to algorithms. These cognitive skills, once lost through disuse, take great time and effort to rebuild. Experts say regulation is urgently needed to try and address these harms.

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